

COLLABORATIVE LEARNING THROUGH MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The article method includes a quantitative analysis whose forum rating was developed by applying a rubric. It is not possible to affirm the superiority of one tool over another because each has its own characteristics and could be used for different purposes, besides having complementary functions, they must organize and complement each other to develop collaborative learning.

Keywords: forums, chat, learning, collaborative.

INTRODUCTION

"Technological progress, and especially information and communication technologies have influenced many fields, one of which is the education sector" [1], bringing consequently changes from routine learning environments to others characterized by constant transformation and innovation.

The importance and purpose of this research lies in knowing the social and ethical impact of collaborative learning tools and at the same time promote the use of these tools in students because in most cases the teaching-learning processes are carried out routinely, through non-participatory methodologies that directly involve students to develop collaborative processes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Web 2.0, e-Learning and Moodle

Web 2.0 [3], is a set of Internet utilities and services that are supported by a database, which can be modified by users of the service. Users can add, change, delete and exchange information, either in the form of presenting them in the content or in both simultaneously. In this context, Web 2.0 combines a variety of learning events with tutorial support to facilitate the transmission of tacit knowledge, [4].

Consequently, Web 2.0 is characterized by the easy management of information, and by promoting a collaborative teaching-learning scheme in which the student is the protagonist of his or her own learning process.

According to [2] currently, the most innovative modality in Web-based distance education are e-Learning systems or environments, which make use of the services and facilities of the Internet, to make the process of collaborative

teaching- learning possible; as well as the Web has enabled educational possibilities at certain levels and with very specific applications.

In this context, e-Learning platforms constitute teaching- learning systems mediated by technology, where one of the fundamental requirements is the existence of an Internet connection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Moodle Tools

According to [1], the tools that distinguish the Moodle virtual learning platform are the Forums, Wikis and Chats; [2], classifies the resources available in Moodle into three categories, to which the communication tools can also be added: (a) Transmissive resources, (b) interactive resources, (c) collaborative resources: Moodle includes the following collaborative tools: Forums, Workshops and Wikis [3], cited by [4], (d) In this context collaborative resources are tools oriented to interaction and exchange of ideas, these tools are forums, wikis, workshops, among others, (e) communication tools [2] available in Moodle are: E-mail, Chats, Messages, Consultations and Surveys.

In this context, chats as well as forums and wikis allow interaction and exchange of ideas among participants, creating collaborative learning environments and teamwork, as it allows interaction between teacher-student and student-student at the same time.

Collaborative Learning

According to [3], collaborative learning enables students to build their own knowledge through a complex interactive process involving three key elements: the students, the content, and the teacher, who acts as facilitator and mediator between the two.

In other words, the student is the active author of the acquisition of his or her own knowledge, through an interactive process in which the content and the teacher are also involved.

According to [4], in order to define a learning environment, it is important to first determine the environment, understanding as environment all that surrounds the teaching- learning process, that is, the space that surrounds the student while participating in said process, constitutes it from material elements such as the infrastructure and facilities of the campus, as well as different factors that directly influence the student such as physical, affective, cultural, political, economic, social, family and even environmental factors; which combine and have a favorable effect or not so much in the student's learning.

In this context, communication between those who are within the teaching-learning process, that is, teacher-students, vice versa, and student-student, measured by the environment that surrounds it and by technologies such as a virtual classroom (CMS Moodle), are environments and factors that often promote the process of collaborative teaching-learning.

CMS Tools that Contribute to the Development of Collaborative Learning

According to [2], the Wiki is an instrument that allows everyone to participate in it; they can be visited, edited or changed. The use of this tool begins to gain strength in the academic field in virtual spaces.

On the other hand [3] they affirm that the student is promoted to develop an autonomous learning, in which, under his responsibility he appropriates his formation, exchanging knowledge and ideas with other students, incorporating himself in this way in a collaborative learning. As opposed to what happens in a classroom, the wiki can extend the notes with the collaboration of all; wikis can also be used in parallel with forums or chat.

In this context [4], he affirms that the use of a virtual classroom contributes to improving students' inter-learning; new resources are integrated that help to improve teaching practice, communication, motivation, and orientation; improving the interaction between teacher-student and student-student.

Likewise [2] virtual learning environments offer an asynchronous learning space that provides students with course materials, as well as collaboration and interaction during the implementation of a virtual forum.

CONCLUSION

- The use of didactic strategies such as Wikis, Forums and Chat in the sessions promote collaborative learning. The main factors for this to happen are the degree of appropriation of these technologies by students and the mastery of their use by teachers.

- The digital divide for the use of these technologies can cause students who do not have access to IT to be disadvantaged.

- Wikis, Forums and Chat encourage and enhance students' reflection on their own practice, in an interactive way, encouraging critical analysis and autonomous and collaborative work.

The experimentation carried out is useful not only for students, but for all teachers who want to promote collaborative learning.

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